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COMPARISON OF THE IDEAL OF MEN IN THE WORKS OF RUSSIAN LITERATURE OF THE 19TH CENTURY

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Annotation: The thesis explores the complex personality of Eugene Onegin, characterized by contradictions, egoism, and a rebellious spirit. Onegin's disillusionment with the empty luxuries of St. Petersburg leads him to seek meaning in literature, rural seclusion, and love. However, his selfishness and indifference prevent him from appreciating the gifts of fate, resulting in tragic consequences. The thesis also discusses the portrayal of Onegin as a representative of the "superfluous people" in Russian literature, who yearn for change but lack the will to act.

Key words: Eugene Onegin, complex personality, contradictions, egoism, rebellious spirit, superfluous people, disillusionment, literature, rural seclusion, love, tragic consequences, Russian literature.

Eugene Onegin's personality is complex, ambiguous, and contradictory. He possesses egoism, vanity, and high demands for himself and the world. Simultaneously, he has a delicate, vulnerable mind and a rebellious spirit seeking freedom. This explosive mixture captivates readers. Introduced at 26, Onegin represents St. Petersburg's golden youth, apathetic and filled with bitter irony. He is tired of luxury, idle idleness, and earthly entertainments. Pushkin reveals

Onegin's disillusionment through his origin, childhood, and adolescence. Onegin was born into an aristocratic rich, but later ruined family, received a rather superficial, detached from the realities of Russian life, but quite typical of that time education, which allowed him to easily speak French, dance the mazurka, bow casually and have pleasant manners for going out.

Plunging into a carefree social life with its entertainments (visiting theaters, balls, restaurants), love affairs, a complete lack of responsibilities and the need to earn a living, Onegin quickly gets fed up and feels a real aversion to the empty and idle tinsel of the capital. He falls into depression (or as it was called then in the "Russian melancholy") and tries to distract himself by finding something to do. First it was a literary test of the pen, which ended in complete failure, then binge reading books, which quickly bored him, and finally flight and voluntary seclusion in the rural wilderness. The pampered lordly upbringing, which did not instill in him a love of work and a lack of willpower, led to the fact that he could not bring any business to its logical conclusion, he spent too much time in idleness and laziness, and such a life spoiled him completely.

Arriving in the village, Onegin avoids the company of neighbors, lives alone and apart. At first, he even tries to make the life of the peasants easier in some way by replacing the serfdom with a "light tax", but old habits affect him and after carrying out a single reform, he becomes bored and sad and he throws everything.

Real gifts of fate (Onegin selfishly did not appreciate them and carelessly discarded them) it became a sincere friendship with Lensky, whom Eugene killed in a duel, and the sublime, bright love of a beautiful girl Tatiana Larina (also rejected). Having become a hostage of public opinion, which he really despised so much, Onegin agrees to a duel with Lensky, who has become a truly close-minded person to him, and fatally wounds him in a duel. Egoism, indifference, indifference to life and spiritual callousness did not allow him to appreciate the great gift of love offered by fate and he remains for life.

A lonely and restless seeker of the meaning of life. Having matured and grown wiser, he meets Tatiana again in St. Petersburg and falls madly in love with

the luxurious and brilliant socialite she has become. But it's too late to change anything, his love is rejected out of a sense of duty and Onegin is left with nothing. The image of Onegin in Russian literature reveals a whole galaxy of heroes, the so-called "superfluous people" who suffer in the reality around them, are in search of new moral and spiritual values. But they are too weak-willed, lazy or selfish to take any real actions that can change their lives for the better. The finale of the work is ambiguous, Onegin remains at a crossroads and can still find himself and perform actions and deeds that will benefit society.

"Gore ot uma" by A. S. Griboyedov is a 1833 comedic verse. Memorable phrases and lines have remained relevant over time. The protagonist, Alexander Chatsky, returns after a three-year journey. Orphaned, he grew up in Famusov's household, his father's friend. Despite their separation, he loves Famusov's daughter, Sophia. However, Sophia is hurt by Chatsky's lack of correspondence and has found a new lover, Alexey Molchalin. Chatsky struggles to understand Sophia's choice and the transformation of an obedient person into a lover. Misunderstood by the Famusov society, Chatsky's ideas and speeches are not comprehended by the older generation. Sophia, offended by his contempt for Molchalin, labels him crazy in anger. This rumor explains Chatsky's peculiar behavior.

Alexander Andreevich Chatsky is a mature young man who understands the foolishness and flattery of others. He is not interested in serving or becoming a bureaucrat, which alarms Famusov, who views him as a Jacobin. Chatsky believes that one can gain respect by devoting oneself to science. He is the only positive character in the story and is intelligent, sarcastic, and capable of love. He values freedom and does not seek the support of the crowd. Chatsky is a true patriot who loves Russia and the Russian language, but is disgusted with how the nobility has corrupted it with French words. Despite his views, he is considered crazy by Famusov's society.

Disadvantages of Chatsky

Chatsky, a highly educated character, is perceptive to society's shortcomings and ridicules others with his competent speech, but it proves to be futile. He is frustrated as people around him are not as intelligent as him, and he is too proud to accept disrespect. Despite his objectivity, he is in love with Sofia Famusova and is blinded by his feelings for her. Chatsky believes in equality and wants to serve his country truthfully, but his perception of people is lifeless, focused only on money. The play showcases the personal conflict of a "new" young man. The standards

of Russian male beauty evolved from a village-oriented physique to a tall, stately, and well-fed gentleman with no rustic blush, caused by a shift from a rural to an urban population. The ideal male beauty of the 19th century resembled a foreign prince with polished nails due to a lifestyle of carousing and idleness. An example of this beauty is found in Eugene Onegin.

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